

Impact of Motivational Testimonies among Student Nurses at Isabela State University-Echague: A Comparative Study

Aldrich Nevin Abad¹, Melisa Bairulla², Marichris Ballad³, Marjorie Carganilla⁴, Alelie Domingo⁵, Mylene Domingo⁶, Jeanette Dungca⁷, Markhipolito P. Galingana⁸, Virgilio A. Ganadin Jr.⁹
Isabela State University Main Campus - College of Nursing, Echague, Isabela, Philippines

Abstract:- The academe's transition to virtual learning makes the current education setup difficult as students were used to the traditional face-to-face resulting in stress due to the adjustments brought upon by the new modality of learning. This motivated the researchers to conduct a study that addresses students' motivational levels by introducing motivational testimonies through an online platform, Entertainment Talk, or E-talk that interviews successful alumni. This study aims to know the impact of conducting an E-talk with successful nurses who went through the same struggles as the present nursing students. A 23-item questionnaire was floated to 82 students through pre-test and post-test in the College of Nursing. The result shows that there is a significant difference $H(3) = 163.438, p = .00$, which in terms of motivation across year levels, 4th-year leads in ranking. It is also found that there is a significant relationship ($r = .608$) between the motivational level of nursing students before and after introducing motivational testimonies. The mean of the pretest (4.0438) and post-test (4.0974) shows the highest motivational level of the participants before and after introducing motivational testimonies. Based on the indicated findings, the motivational level of participants has affected their profile. Student nurses aged 22-24 years old and Female participants dominated in increased motivational level. This means that Motivational Testimonies through the use of E-talk improved or increased the students' motivational level.

Keywords:- Motivation, E-Talk, Student Nurses, Motivational Testimonies.

I. INTRODUCTION (BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY)

Motivation is viewed as a significant element of academic and professional success. Motivation is the fuel that ignites abilities and propels them to accomplish goals. Although innate talent is a predictor of success, motivation is an agent that allows those abilities to be utilized to achieve great accomplishments, whether in school or in the workplace. An ability or talent can't be turned into a performance without the presence of motivation. An ability without motivation is

meaningless, much as a windmill without air is (McCoach & Flake 2018). Nursing students are the future major workforce of the health industry. Their academic perception is important for them to develop the needed knowledge, skills, and attitude to become competent nurses. The degree is intensive because the life of every patient is at stake, hence effort and focus must be unrelenting. The academe's transition from traditional face-to-face to virtual learning makes the current education setup difficult for students as everyone is not used to this method of education. During the adjustment period, the frustration and anxiety of students are demonstrated by their inability to meet and carry out school requirements (Conway, 2019).

Academic tasks through their quizzes, lectures, activities, assignments, return demonstrations in clinical subjects, and examinations are areas that are required completion (Friels, 2016). According to Rotas & Cahapay (2020), these requirements are often not fulfilled and accomplished due to a variety of factors including the instability of internet connection, power shortage, or the environmental setup of a student, which are vital elements when it comes to the new modality of learning. As a response to the emergence of the COVID-19 pandemic, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) in the Philippines, issued a memorandum that orders flexible learning to reduce the risk of infection in school. This major shift of learning modality was a necessity for the greater good but this caused a great impact on the learning process of the students causing fatigue and lack of motivation in attending classes as well as doing school tasks due to prolonged exposure to virtual meetings burdened by unstable internet connectivity (Oducado, Fajardo, Maniago, Villanueva, Dequilla, Montano, Robite, 2021).

Furthermore, students have suffered from varying amounts of stress over unexpected events inside and outside their community. This is evident in the result of a study conducted by Fawaz (2020), showing that due to the sudden shift to online learning, there was an increase in the prevalence of depression and anxiety among undergraduate university students due to the demanding load of work required. The study conducted by Davion (2017), revealed the significance of teachers in providing an environment that encourages students to learn. In addition, it is also mentioned that teachers

have the capacity to improve students' interest in a specified subject as well as their competency. However, the shift in learning modality created a communication barrier between the students and educators, which is challenging for both sides.

The transition to online learning affected and challenged the students as they were used to traditional face-to-face learning. However, it is equally important to find out how the difficulties of the students during this new modality of learning, like how the lack of motivation can be addressed for their personal and academic well-being. E-talk is a tool used to deliver motivational testimonies virtually by the alumni of Isabela State University, College of Nursing. It is a platform where they can share their experiences and the challenges, they've been through to reach where they are now. In this light, this study aims to know the impact of conducting an E-talk with the successful nurses who went through the same struggles as the present nursing students in the hope that it can help students have optimism and find ways in order to overcome their struggles and envision themselves through the right path. It strives to give a gratifying ambiance that helps students become driven to study again in a positive spirit, aiming to boost the nursing students' courage.

Also, this study aims to contribute knowledge to the nursing practice and profession by means of a better engagement in nursing education as this study gives importance to the mental health of student nurses as they continue to achieve their dreams in this type of learning setup.

II. METHODS

The research employs a causal-comparative design. It is a research design that seeks to find out the correlation between the independent and dependent variables after an event has occurred. The independent variable is the testimonies of the alumni and the dependent variable is the level of motivation. The researcher's goal is to determine the impact of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The researchers collected data before and after exposure to the independent variable and compare the data of each of the different year levels. The study was conducted at the Isabela State University–Main Campus, College of Nursing, Barangay San Fabian, Echague, Isabela since the chosen participants are nursing students at the University. The total population of the students is 530. The methods of teaching used are modular and limited face-to-face learning. This study used a non-probability sampling technique which is a convenient sampling in determining the participants. The participants who voluntarily engaged in the said E-talk become the participants of the study. In this study, the overall population of the Nursing students of the Isabela State University- Echague is 530 and is divided into 4 subgroups specifically based on their year level (1st year to 4th year). There were 21 students in the first year, 18 in the second year, 21 in the third year, and 22 in the fourth year were the one who voluntarily participated in conducting the motivational testimonies. A total of 82 participants were utilized in this

study.

For the purpose of this study, the researchers used a student motivation scale based on the study by Martin (2001) titled "The Student Motivation Scale: A Tool for Measuring and Enhancing Motivation". The questionnaire is composed of five 'Boosters' and five 'Guzzlers', which the author used to measure the factors enhancing (boosters) and reducing (guzzlers) motivation of students and separate it through thoughts/feelings and behaviors. 'Booster thoughts' are evaluated through self-belief, learning focus, and value of schooling; while 'booster behaviors' are evaluated through persistence and planning, and monitoring; 'guzzler thoughts/feelings' are assessed through anxiety and low control; and, 'guzzler behaviors' are assessed through avoidance and self-sabotage. The questionnaire was used to know the comparison on the impact of motivational testimonies among nursing students in the different year levels. Since this is an exploratory study knowing the different impacts of motivational testimonies, the use of a school survey based on the questionnaire is that it allows the researchers some flexibility in the way they modify questions for each individual participant. It also gives the researchers the opportunity to provide more information and clarification when necessary.

After the pilot testing was conducted, the instrument underwent a content-validity test by a statistician in which a 0.77 reliability was yielded using Cronbach alpha.

TABLE 1. Cronbach Alpha

Subscale	N	Item	Cronbach α	Internal consistency
Boosters	30	13	0.87	Good
Guzzlers	30	10	0.89	Good
Questionnaire	30	21	0.77	Acceptable

The researchers selected an alumnus to be a guest at the E-talk. They contacted them through their Facebook accounts and got their approval to be a guest on the said program. The platform used during the E-talk was Stream Yard.

The following shows the flow of the data-gathering procedure;

- The researchers secured the permit to conduct the study at the College of Nursing at Isabela State University - Echague, specifically from the Dean of the College of Nursing.
- After securing the necessary permit or approval to conduct the study, the researchers requested the Dean to issue a memo encouraging the faculty to make the participation of students in the sitcom to be included in their requirements or as a bonus requirement, if possible.
- The researchers prepared the data gathering tool needed for this study which is an adopted

- questionnaire and invited them to become a guest for a 30-minute sitcom for each session.
- The pretest questionnaire was floated on May 3, 2022, through an online platform which is Google Forms, to be sent via messenger to all nursing students who voluntarily agreed to become a participant.
- The researchers conducted an activity, an E-talk with an Alumnus, which was held on May 7 and 17, 2022, Saturday at 7:00 pm wherein all nursing students of Isabela State University - Echague are part of the audience. The attendance was strictly monitored by the researchers.
- The researchers disseminated again the questionnaires after the sitcom through an online platform which was Google form, sent via messenger to the nursing students of the College of Nursing at Isabela State University – Echague who voluntarily engaged to become a participant, and the researchers also ensured the participants that their identity and answers will be confidential.

In analyzing the data gathered, the following statistical tools were used. The quantitative approach was used to pursue the objectives of the present study and all the data that were gathered by the researchers were statistically analyzed. **Percentage Distribution.** This was used to determine the demographic profile of the participants in a Comparative Study on the Impact of Motivational Testimonies among different year levels of Nursing Students at Isabela State University-Echague. **Mean and Standard Deviation.** This described the level of motivation of the participants. **Pearson's R Correlation.** This was employed to test the significant relationship between the respondent's levels of motivation. It is based on the method of covariance, it is regarded as the best method for determining the relationship between variables of interest (Statistics Solution, 2022).

TABLE 2. Pearson's R Correlation

	Level of Correlation
0.80 – 1.0	Very strong
0.60 – 0.799	Strong
0.40 – 0.599	Strong enough
0.20 – 0.399	Weak
0.00 – 0.199	Very Weak

Kruskal Wallis. Finally, this was utilized to find out the significant difference in the level of motivation across year levels after introducing motivation testimonies. We, the researchers, ensured that the components of our study adhere to all the ethical principles of a research study.

This includes honesty in all the data, results, methods, and procedures presented and used in our research. This also means that this study does not falsify or fabricate data. The researchers were objective in terms of data analysis, data interpretation, and other aspects that require the researchers to be objective to avoid bias. We were also careful throughout the

research process to prevent errors and to critically examine our own work. The researchers also shared the data gathered, the result, tools, and resources, and were open to criticism and new ideas. Acknowledgment and proper credit from all sources and people who contributed to the research were given. The rights of all participants of this research study are respected, including their right to full disclosure, self-determination, and privacy. **Right to full disclosure.** The participants' information is not disclosed to anyone except the members of the research group who will evaluate the data. **Right to self-determination.** The researchers ensured that informed consent was given and their decisions of whether they wanted to be part of our research study or not, were respected. **Right to privacy.** Names were optional in the questionnaire to protect the anonymity and privacy of the participants.

III. RESULTS

TABLE 3. Distribution of demographic profile of participants in terms of Age, Gender, and Year

PROFILE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Age		
18	7	8.53%
19	19	23.17%
20	24	29.26%
21	18	21.95%
22	12	14.63%
23	1	1.21%
24	1	1.21%
Gender		
Male	14	17.07%
Female	68	82.92%
Year Level		
1 st Year	21	25.0%
2 nd Year	18	21.95%
3 rd Year	21	25.60%
4 th Year	22	26.82%

Table 3 shows that 7 out of 82 participants (8.53%) are 18 years old, 19 (23.17%) are 19 years old, 24 (29.26%) are 20 years old, 18 (21.95%) are 21 years old, 12 (14.63%) are 22 years old, 1 (1.21%) is 23 years old, and 1 (1.21%) is 24 years old. In terms of gender, 14 out of the 82 participants (17.07%) are male and 68 (82.92%) are female. And for the year level, 21 of the participants (25%) are in 1st year, 18 (21.95%) are in 2nd year, 21 (25.60%) are in 3rd year, and 22 (26.82%) are in 4th year. Therefore, the analysis of the data gathered reveals that the highest contributor of participants was taken from those at the age of 20 years old (29.26 percent). The data gathered conveys that the male student nurses are dominated by female student nurses (82.92%), and there were 22 or 26.82% among the participants are from 4th year-level nursing students.

TABLE 4. *The level of motivation grouped according to the profile*

	Pretest	Posttest
Age		
18-19	4.09	4.035
20-21	4	4.15
22-24	4.25	4.305
Gender		
Male	4.03	4.035
Female	4.05	4.34
Year Level		
1 st year	4.09	4.09
2 nd year	4.01	3.99
3 rd year	4.01	4.11
4 th year	4.05	4.18

The table shows that nursing students at the age of 22-24 have increased their motivational level more than those younger nursing students after being introduced to motivational testimonies. Gender is correlated to the change in motivational level after being introduced to motivational testimonies. As evidenced by the result of the posttest for female participants, the increase in their motivational level is greater than that of the male participants. Moreover, the motivational level of the 2nd year participants decreased after being introduced to motivational testimonies, unlike the other three-year levels have shown an increase in their motivational level after the said testimonies, with the 4th year students having the highest result.

According to the study of Mthimunye (2019), female and older clients were found to be more associated with higher academic performance and success. Hence, indicating that they are more motivated than males and younger ones.

TABLE 5. *Motivational level of the participants before and after introducing motivational testimonies*

	\bar{x}	Standard Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
Pretest	4.0438	0.3135	Motivated
Posttest	4.0974	0.3003	Motivated

The table above shows the result of motivational testimonies. The motivational level is considered as highly motivated if the mean value is at 5, motivated if at 4-4.9, moderately motivated if at 3-3.9, demotivated if at 2-2.9 and severely demotivated if at 1-1.9. The mean for the pretest is 4.0 which shows a motivated verbal interpretation, while the mean for the post-test is 4.0974 which also indicates a motivated verbal interpretation. The Alpha 0.5 is the confidence level. As the standard deviation gets closer to 0, the most accurate responses to the mean are obtained. Therefore, the standard deviations in the pretest and posttest which are 0.3135 and 0.3003 respectively, convey the accuracy of the

responses to the mean. Jose (2020), which was a participant in Angela Duckworth’s testimony in an E-talk, stated that she has learned a lot. One way she can relate is in her passion, grit, and perseverance in coding and learning new things. This proves that motivational testimonies are capable of improving the motivational level of an individual.

TABLE 6. *The significant relationship between the level of motivation before and after introducing motivational testimonies*

Pearson Correlation	.608**
p-value	.000
Interpretation	Strong Relationship

The Pearson Correlation indicates if there is any significant relationship involved in the Pretest and Posttest. The value .608* implies that there is a strong relationship, wherein it is greater in the p-value which is .000. Therefore, there is a strong relationship between the level of motivation before and after introducing motivational testimonies.

TABLE 7. *The significant difference in the level of motivation across year levels after introducing motivational testimonies*

Year Level	Mean	Post-test	Ranking
1 st	4.09	Motivated	3 rd
2 nd	3.99	Moderately motivated	4 th
3 rd	4.11	Motivated	2 nd
4 th	4.18	Motivated	1 st

The table above indicates the difference in the level of motivation of the nursing students across year levels after introducing motivational testimonies. Ranking 1st is the 4th-year nursing students, 2nd for the 3rd-year nursing students, 3rd for the 1st-year nursing students, and 4th for the 2nd-year nursing students. Kruskal Wallis was a tool used to compare 3 or more groups to answer the research question. (Dr. Haidel, E., 2022). Therefore, there is a significant difference $H(3) = 163.438, p = .00$ among the motivational level of the nursing students after undergoing motivational testimonies.

IV. SUMMARY

The researchers wanted to know how motivational testimonies from the school’s alumni would impact the motivational level of the students. The research design that we used was a causal-comparative design wherein we collected and compared data from each of the participants before and after the introduction of motivational testimonies. The collection was through a survey using Google Forms and the motivational testimonies were provided via E-talk or

webinar. The locale of the study was Isabela State University Echague campus and the participants numbered 21 for the 1st year level, 18 for the 2nd, 21 for the 3rd and, 22 for the 4th. For the questionnaire, the researchers used a student motivational scale based on the study of Martine (2001), the Student Motivation Scale: A Tool for Measuring and Enhancing Motivation. After collecting data, the result showed that the demographic data in terms of the age group ranged from 18-24 years old with 68 females and 14 males.

The level of motivation when grouped according to profile reveals that the age 22-24 have increased their motivational level than those younger nursing students after being introduced to motivational testimonies. In gender, females' motivational level is greater than that of the male participants. Moreover, the motivational level of the 2nd year participants decreased after being introduced to motivational testimonies, unlike the other three-year levels have shown an increase in their motivational level after the said testimonies, with the 4th year students having the highest result. The motivational level of the participants before introducing motivational testimonies was considered 'Motivated' (4.0438). Then, after introducing motivational testimonies, the level of motivation is 4.0974 which is also considered 'Motivated'.

Using Pearson's R Correlation, the researchers interpreted the collected data, stating that there was a strong relationship between the motivational level of nursing students before and after the E-talk wherein the result is .608. Therefore, the finding showed the rejection of our first hypothesis, as well as the second, since there was a significant difference between the motivational level of nursing students before and after introducing motivational testimonies, wherein the result from the 4th year students was ranked 1st, 3rd year as the 2nd, 1st year as the 3rd, and the 2nd year as the 4th.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

- The findings revealed that there is a strong relationship between the respondent's profiles to their level of motivation. The participants' level of motivation is affected by their year level, age, and gender.
- The result showed that the level of motivation of the participants before introducing motivational testimonies is "motivated" (4.0438) and after introducing motivational testimonies is "motivated" (4.0974). The result shows an increased motivational level.
- The findings revealed that there is a significant relationship between the participants' level of motivation before and after introducing motivational testimonies.
- The result showed that there is a significant difference in the motivational level of the nursing students after

undergoing motivation testimonies.

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of the study, the following were strongly recommended:

- Improve the motivational levels of students upon introducing motivational talks.
- Motivational testimonies must be administered continuously to students to increase their self-determination to study and achieve their goals in life.
- The researchers recommend having motivational testimonies be done in a face-to-face setting as well as conducting data gathering.
- For future researchers, conducting similar motivational programs like this in some other local schools, is even better if implemented for younger students.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

With a grateful heart, the authors wish to express their sincerest appreciation and profound gratitude to the following people who generously extended their utmost help that led to the successful completion of this research; Sir Markhipolito P. Galingana, Research Adviser, for his valuable suggestions and endless moral support which greatly contributed to the completion of our research; Sir Virgilio Ganadin Jr., and Sir Jennifer Justo, for their intellectual guidance, fortifying heart, deep concern, and encouragement over this research work; Ma'am Kimberly B. Bassig, English Critic, and Ma'am Nicole Kris L. Silva, Statistician, for their assistance, and constructive criticisms for the improvement of the manuscript; To the College of Nursing Students and Alumni who helped us in sharing their time, effort, and knowledge for us to gather more information. This research would not have been the same without their help and guidance. Thank you for believing in us even when we did not know how we were ever going to get through this. And finally, we would like to extend our profound gratitude to our Almighty God. We would not be here without Him. He has provided us with the abilities, perseverance, and courage to keep going. All credit goes to Him.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Conway, G. (2019) School Connectedness and Academic Buoyancy: Insight into Filipino College Students' Experience of Academic Stress. *Southeast Asia Psychology Journal* Vol. 7.
- [2]. Davion, J. (2017). The Role of Teacher in Motivating Students to Learn. *BU Journal of Graduate Studies in Education*. <https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1230415>
- [3]. Friels, A. C. (2016). Motivation towards success: A qualitative comparative study illustrating the differences in motivating factors in achievement between low Ses high achieving and low African American high school

- females. *Doctoral Dissertation*.
<https://scholarcommons.sc.edu/etd/3437/>
- [4]. Fawaz, M., Samaha, A. (2020). E-learning: Depression, Anxiety, and Stress Symptomatology among Lebanese University Students during COVID-19 Quarantine.
- [5]. *Wiley Online Library*.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/nuf.12521>
- [6]. McCoach, D. B., & Flake, J. K. (2018). The Role of Motivation. *American Psychological Association*.
- [7]. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0000038-013>
- [8]. Oducado, R.M., Fajardo, M.T., Lachica, G., Maniago, J., Villanueva, P.M., Dequilla, M.A.C., Montano, H., Robite, E. (2021). Predictors of Videoconference Fatigue: Results from Undergraduate Nursing Students in the Philippines. *Asian Journal for Public Opinion Research*.
- [9]. Rotas, E., Cahapay, M. (2020). Difficulties in Remote Learning: Voices of Philippine University Students in the Wake of COVID-19 Crisis. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 2020.
<https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1285295.pdf>